

Conceptualizing boundary formation in sacred landscapes: case studies from sacred groves in Northern Epirus, Greece

Valentino Marini Govigli¹, Jennifer L.G. Wong², Kalliopi Stara³, Rigas Tsiakiris⁴, John R. Healey⁵, John M. Halley⁶

¹ vagovigli@cc.uoi.gr, Department of Biological applications and technologies, University of Ioannina, Greece

² Wild Resources Limited, Bangor, UK

³ Department of Biological applications and technologies, University of Ioannina, Greece

⁴ Forestry Service of Ioannina, Greece

⁵ School of Environment, Natural Resources and Geography, College of Natural Sciences, Bangor University, UK

⁶ Department of Biological applications and technologies, University of Ioannina, Greece

Abstract

Investigating the structure of ecological boundaries is a crucial issue for forest research to understand how adjacent systems interact and exchange flows of resources, both spatially and temporally. Their appraisal is, however, challenging, especially in landscapes where cultural and social variables strongly influence boundary configuration.

Among the Mediterranean cultural landscapes, sacred groves in Northern Epirus are a notable example of a long-term coupled socio-ecological system. Their current structure is thought to result from centuries of interaction between the push of social processes (religious taboos, community protection status, local management practices, rural land abandonment) and ecological responses (presence of forest patches in the landscape, changes in plant growth form, increase in tree life spans, infilling of secondary vegetation). The impact of these processes on boundary properties make an excellent case study of coupled human and natural systems, to investigate if the ecological sacred forest structure is depicted by the history of local communities' rules and practices.

Adopting a multidisciplinary approach, we sampled the age and size structure of the sacred grove of Agios Nikolaos (Northern Epirus, Greece), mapped topography, determined viewsheds, and obtained anthropological and historical data from documents, maps and interviews with community members. The results suggest that local management and social norms are critical in structuring the landscape of sacred groves, with current vegetation boundaries still influenced by the legacy of historic sacred-grove management.

Further research will include modeling of the social-ecological interface to predict the future effects of land abandonment on sacred forest spatial structure; developing and testing a flexible tool that could be adapted to other socio-ecological contexts.

Keywords: CHANS, Cultural Landscapes, Greece, Sacred Groves, Socio-Ecological Boundaries.

Introduction, scope and main objectives

Ecological boundaries are defined by (Cadenasso *et al.* 2003a) as those areas “of transition, contact, or separation between the contrasting elements of a mosaic”. Boundaries, as spatial phenomena evolving in time, are characterized by two main components: their *structure* - the varying gradient of the variable generating the contrast (*e.g.* altitude), and their *function* - the flow of resources between the two contrasting habitat patches (*e.g.* different habitat types) (Strayer *et al.* 2003; Cadenasso *et al.* 2003b; Laurance *et al.* 2001). Improving understanding of the ecological role that such transition

zones play in the mosaic is thus fundamental in the paradigm of a dynamic landscape impacted by habitat fragmentation. Their appraisal is however, challenging, especially in those socio-ecological landscapes where cultural and social variables strongly influence boundary configuration.

Sacred groves are a particular case of long-term social-ecological systems. Such classifications, often named coupled human and natural systems (CHANS), are research frameworks that aim to investigate how nature and social communities interact reciprocally at a landscape level, building adaptive, dynamics, and complex feedback circuits (Alessa *et al.* 2008; Liu *et al.* 2007). CHANS-based research encompasses a variety of different habitat types, and different levels of interactions among the social and the ecological actors (Alberti *et al.* 2011). Sacred groves are additionally characterised by being Sacred Natural Sites, natural areas that hold special spiritual and/or religious meaning to local people and communities (Oviedo and Jeanrenaud 2007).

Understanding boundary configurations in such systems is complex, due to the tight interactions amongst ecological and cultural processes. CHANS' boundaries are often the combination of definite and often bi-dimensional socio-political and cultural traits (*e.g.* anthropogenic partitioning constructions, administrative demarcation lines, cultural and local land use conventions), smoother ecological attributes (*e.g.* habitat patches) and distinct physical features (*e.g.* slope). Likewise, the boundaries of Epirus sacred groves are thought to result from centuries of interaction between social processes (*e.g.* religious taboos, community protection status, local management practices, rural land abandonment), ecological responses (*e.g.* change in plant growth form, increase in tree life spans, infilling of secondary vegetation), and the physical constraints of the landscape (*e.g.* altitude, topography).

The role of cultural perception towards the environment is also a key factor in the determination of CHANS boundaries (Brown and Raymond 2007; Zhu *et al.* 2010). Perceptual boundaries embrace all the characteristics previously delineated for ecological boundaries: they are defined by a varying gradient (how we discern emotionally the environment itself, *i.e.* through fear, respect, etc), and they enclose a flow of resource, which corresponds to the difference in behaviour that would be appropriate in a perceived dissimilar environment (*e.g.* if we trespass or not in such an environment). In this regards, one working hypothesis arising from the interviews conducted, is that the viewshed (the area from which it can be seen) of an outlying church or icon stand symbolize the area over which the presence of the Virgin or Saint subjugates the forces of nature. Such perceptual constrain could hence have acted as a powerful spiritual boundary which may have contributed to generate the current extent of the grove (Nixon 2006; Stara *et al.* 2015).

The objective of this research is to build an innovative framework to better understand the boundaries of CHANS based on the specific case of sacred forests, taking into consideration also how people's perception could play a significant role in boundaries characterization. Our framework follows that outlined by Cadenasso *et al.* (2003a):

- a. to identify factors controlling boundaries;
- b. to link boundary structure with boundary function;
- c. to compare and assimilate anthropogenic and ecological features in boundary definition.

In order to achieve this, we intensively studied a sacred grove in the region of Epirus, northwestern Greece: *Livadakia*, a sacred grove dedicated to *Agios Nikolaos* (St. Nicholas) (abbreviated as LAN). Our approach involved: mapping of all large trees in the grove through adaptive cluster sampling, dendrochronology of tree cores, GIS representations of the landscape and collection of anthropological and historical data obtained from documents, maps and interviews with community members.

Methodology/approach

Study site

The grove of LAN is situated on a gently-sloping hill at 850-950 m altitude. The site comprises two main plant communities: broadleaved woodland dominated by deciduous oaks (*Q. cerris* and *Q. frainetto*, with more sparse *Q. pubescens*), and a thick shrub layer composed of prickly oak (*Q. coccifera*), and juniper (*J. oxycedrus*) (Korakis *et al.* 2014). According to the local tradition, LAN used to be the sacred grove of a small settlement for which Agios Nikolaos was its church (Fig.1). The former settlement was abandoned around the 17th century when the inhabitants moved to the nearby village Vitsa (Nikolaidis, 1939) (Fig.1). LAN is protected as the peripheral grove of the former village as well as wood reserve and for aesthetic purposes. The main community management rules comprised prohibition of cutting live trees and foliage for fodder, and controlled grazing (Stara *et al.* 2014, *unpublished report*).

Fig. 1: Location of LAN sacred grove in the Epirus Region, Greece.

Data collection and mapping

In order to investigate the structure of LAN boundaries, a definite framework was followed. This involved: data collection of the main ecological feature believed to be the core of the current forest (large trees), inclusion of social data, and lastly the development of spatial and visual tools able to verify the extents of such zones.

Linear boundaries of LAN as defined by Tsiakiris *et al.* (2014) were taken as input for the study. Such boundaries were generated from ortho-rectified aerial photographs of the year 1945, when the sacred groves in the area were clearly visible as isolated patches of a vividly used landscape. However, the tree sampling scheme was not constrained by these limits and extended 50 m beyond them in order to examine the boundary nature.

A two-stage tree inventory was undertaken using a systematic sampling followed by adaptive cluster sampling (ACS; Thompson 2002). The systematic sampling was designed with a square grid system (cell size 15x15 m) with 60 m spacing. In each plot the main tree variables recorded were tree species,

and diameter at breast height. The rationale for using ACS was that ancient protected trees tend to be distributed in clusters around the core zones of the grove (*e.g.* centre, church or icon-stand). For all the plots systematically sampled in step 1, only a subset n was selected as the initial sample for ACS. The target element was the presence of trees with diameter at 1.3 m ($d_{1.3}$) \geq 40 cm, or stumps with basal diameter (d_0) \geq 50 cm. For each of these plots, a second set of plots was laid out adjacent to each edge, continuing the process until none of the new plots included the target element. GPS coordinates for all trees sampled were recorded. Results of the forest sampling were mapped into GIS, as well as prominent features of the landscape (*e.g.* the church).

Wood cores were extracted from a total of 54 undamaged deciduous oaks (*Q. cerris*, *Q. frainetto*, *Q. pubescens*). These trees were sampled during the first stage of the sampling scheme, by coring the deciduous oak with the second biggest size in each plot, so as to avoid largest trees more likely to be hollow or rotten in the centre (White 1998). Additional trees were cored at a later stage to fill gaps in the range of diameter size. Cores were taken following the procedure outlined in Phipps (1985). Mounted cores were then dried and polished with progressively finer grades of sandpaper. Tree ages were determined by counting backwards from the first ring behind the bark to the pith. If the core missed the pith, the number of missing rings was estimated assuming a homocentric growth of tree rings equal to the average width of the 10th innermost existing ring, using functions available in CooRecorder software (CooRecorder 2013). Trees were subsequently classified into bounded age classes. All forestry data were collected between June and September 2014.

The social data available for LAN comprises interviews with inhabitants of Vitsa and literature review of the village history data. 10 Interviews on the sacred grove were undertaken in the Vitsa area during 2003 (2 interviews), 2006 (7) and 2014 (2). Additional information was obtained from manuscripts and monographs about local history and folklore.

The relationship of tree age and diameter was tested by linear regression to determine if age can be estimated from diameter with sufficient accuracy for the remaining un-cored sampled trees. The data collected were used to realize a land use map of the area, and to produce a viewshed analysis generated with ArcMap functionalities (ESRI 2015). The input DEM layer for viewshed analyses was derived from a GPS survey conducted in LAN comprising a grid of 800 altitudinal points recorded with 6 m spacing, integrated with the available ASTER global DEM (30m spacing).

Results

The ACS recorded 233 trees with $d_{1.3}$ over 40 cm (and 7 stumps) in the LAN grove. These trees are concentrated in the vicinity of the church, with an average tree distance of $77.1 \text{ m} \pm 2.2 \text{ SE}$ from it (Fig.2). Dominant species are *Q. frainetto* (150 individuals) and *Q. cerris* (61 individuals). Viewshed analysis shows that the majority of the trees located with the ACS are at eyesight distance from the Church of Agios Nikolaos (72% of all trees) (Fig.3). For the deciduous oaks cored, there was a significant linear regression relationship between $d_{1.3}$ and age ($R^2=0.76$; $F=173.4$; $d.f.=1,52$; $p<0.05$, regression equation: $\text{age} = 3.48 \text{ } d_{1.3} - 12.80$). The regression coefficient was used to assign an estimated age class to all deciduous oaks sampled with the ACS (Fig.4).

A land-use map of LAN was produced by merging ACS results with available information on management practices and social data (Fig. 4). The map shows that the extension of the current woodland stretches from S towards the NE edge of the 1945's boundaries. On the other hand, areas towards the W and NE edges show a higher level of current human interference in term of grazing intensity.

The core of LAN is an old oak woodland which comprises four age classes of trees, an ancient cohort of 6 individuals (aged between 350 and 450 years old), a mature (between 250 and 350 years old) cohort of 28 individuals, a medium-aged (between 150 and 250 years old) cohort of 112 trees, and a young (90 - 150 years old) cohort of 80 individuals. There was a significant effect of age class on the

distance to the church (Kruskal Wallis $\chi^2 = 28.05$; $d.f. = 3$; $p < 0.01$). Specifically “mature” trees were significantly closer to the church than “medium-aged” trees (Mann-Whitney post-hoc test with Bonferroni correction, $p < 0.01$) and “young” trees ($p < 0.01$).

Fig. 2: Results of the ACS mapping in LAN. Diameter at breast height ($d_{1.3}$) was recorded for standing trees, basal diameter (d_0) for stumps.

Fig. 3: Viewshed map of LAN from the church of Agios Nikolaos.

Fig. 4: Land use map of LAN. Tree age classes are classified as follows: Young (50-150 years old), Medium-aged (150-250); Mature (250-350) and Ancient (350-450). The variable Grazing (plots with high and very high grazing intensity) and Anthropogenic cuts (plots with presence of cut branches) were recorded during the first stage of the sampling.

Discussion

The LAN site conforms to the theory that sacred groves are determined by the dynamic interaction of three main sets of processes: physical, ecological and socio-cultural. In LAN, the results obtained seem to follow this working theory, with its configuration being shaped by topographical arrangement, former protection status of the site and grazing management practices.

If we consider LAN boundaries as demarcated simply by the extent of the area characterized by large trees, then the results obtained with the ACS show that the extent of the grove is dissimilar to the one generated by Tsiakiris *et al.* (2014). In particular, the grove encloses a smaller area respect to the one included in 1945's boundaries, excluding a large block to the west (Fig.2). In addition, the location of the grove's mature trees in proximity to the church is typical of existing sacred sites in which the church, together with icon stands or other religious structures, are often identified as the cultural centre of the site itself (Lagopoulos 2002). The tree survey shows an extension of tree cover beyond the former LAN boundary towards the NE (Fig.2). However, these trees seem to be spatially located as relict hedgerows of former grazing or agricultural land, hence indicating a different socio-ecological system.

Around the core area of LAN there are two areas in which no trees larger than 40cm are present, with one (W of the church) included in the former boundary. These two areas are characterized by sparse shrubland communities of *Q. coccifera*, steep slopes and a thick layer of regolith (area in yellow in Fig.4). Such terrain is quite common in Greece, and in other areas of the Mediterranean basin (*e.g.* Continental Italy, SE of Spain; Grove and Rackham 2001). Stream, wind and animal trampling erosion, as well as geology are probably among the main causes of such shrubland systems. With respect to animal trampling, there is evidence from the data collected, that shepherds move their herds

(goats, sheep and cows) from the village of Vitsa down to grazing land close to LAN during the summer period. Although the socio-ecological interaction in LAN has changed with respect to last centuries, due to demographic decline and rural economic transformations (Zomeni *et al.* 2008), it seems that reduction in grazing pressure on these zones has not yet led to a successional change from sparse shrubland into a different ecological community. This suggests that the role played by animal trampling is not fully responsible for the maintenance of the condition of such environments.

The theory of perceptual boundaries seems to have ground in LAN. The majority of the trees are indeed at eye distance with the church as shown by Fig.3. However it is not yet clear if this configuration has been determined by the spiritual and perceptual constrains or by topographical factors. Eyesight distance and altitude are variables that tend to influence one another. The church is quite visible from its surrounding mainly because it is located around the top of the hill that characterises LAN sacred grove. In addition, it is also visible from the southern area most likely because there the slope of the hill is less steep respect to the others directions. Nevertheless LAN topographical arrangement, an isolated hill in a generally flat environment, could have facilitated the community leaders to better define its former boundaries, and for the community to respect it.

Conclusions/outlook

The main purpose of this study was to extend the current knowledge of boundary formation of CHANS following the framework outlined by Cadenasso *et al.* (2003a).

It is possible to conclude that:

- a. the current boundary configuration of LAN is the result of a set of diverse socio-ecological processes that, combined, contributed to influence its structure;
- b. such processes have played an important role in differentiating the vegetation habitats of LAN, with woodland communities located in the core and shrublands in the outer zones;
- c. anthropological aspects such as grazing management practices and perceptual constrains might have played an important role in the dynamics of LAN boundaries.

Despite some methodological limitations (approximation of tree age classes, limitation of the sampling scheme), this research has successfully provided the basis to better understand fuzzy boundary dynamics of sacred groves. Additional case studies need to be investigated in order to develop and test the methodology. Further research is currently under way to model socio-ecological interactions, in order to better comprehend the factors controlling sacred grove formation and predict the future structure of such delicate cultural systems under different conservation scenarios.

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